

Designing an optimal future Peatland Monitoring Framework for Scotland

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Executive summary

This report forms part of the deliverables of WorkPackage 1 of the JHI-D3-2 (CentrePeat, 2022-2027) project. We explored the potential for a low-cost national Peatland Monitoring Network for Scotland, which would address the current lack of coverage of sites not under any nature designation scheme, and simultaneously provide robust evidence that could be used to verify Earth Observation-based models of condition as well as the likely greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions as per the categorisation used in UK Greenhouse Gas Inventory reporting for peatlands. Given the focus of Work Package 1 on GHG emissions proxies, we focused here on developing a possible network of monitoring locations that could be used to better inform national statistics of the current emissions from peatlands. We assessed a number of possible solutions for an ‘ideal’ distribution of 100 network site locations, that best represented the need to proportionally represent the land cover of different condition classes on peat across Scotland and its’ climatic and socio-economic gradients, but also provided the best option in terms of providing additional evidence to calculate more robust emissions statistics. The resulting potential network was assessed relative to existing monitoring efforts for site condition, GHG emissions, and restoration effectiveness. Finally, the network was evaluated in terms of the minimum number of low-cost data loggers, in this case water table depth monitoring, equipment needs, frequency of sampling, and the likely cost implications of such a network. The potential co-benefits of such a network to also provide critical data for a site condition monitoring effort through Earth Observations are briefly discussed, but a more detailed report on this will be completed by the end of February 2023 as a deliverable from Work Package 2 of the same project.

Introduction

Peatlands cover nearly a quarter of Scotland's land area and store nearly 50% of all its soil carbon. Enhancing and protecting the health of peatlands is key to reaching Scotland's net zero target, given that current evidence suggests that the majority (>70%) of Scotland's approximately 2.4 million ha of peat is degraded. Collectively, Scottish peatlands emit so much carbon, estimated at around 6.4 Mt CO₂ equivalents (CO₂e) for the latest available figures (2020), that they almost offset the entire forest carbon sink (estimated at -6.95 Mt CO₂e) in Scotland¹. This figure may carry significant uncertainty due to the remaining variability in emission factors and also estimates of the areas of peatland in different condition classes, but is nevertheless clearly a figure of considerable magnitude when considering that the total of all territorial emissions in Scotland in 2020 were estimated to be 40 Mt CO₂e² and that peatlands in undamaged condition are likely to be net carbon neutral or small sinks¹.

Peatland degradation comes in a spectrum ranging from relatively low density of human drainage in an effort to improve the land for e.g., grazing, or relatively localised impacts of e.g., domestic peat extraction, to more severe forms such as peat erosion, or, at the extreme end, complete conversion to e.g., plantation forestry, grassland, agricultural land or widescale peat extraction. In the case of these most extreme scenarios, so much peat may have been lost that the area would no longer qualify as peat under the current Scottish definition of peat soil, which requires a depth of 50 cm.

Alongside the current state as a net carbon emitting land use sector due to the high proportion of degraded peatlands, degradation impacts other vital ecosystem functions such as water filtration/storage, leading to economic impacts on water treatment costs and water security or flood protection. Biodiversity impacts can range from decreased resilience to extreme events, which can lead to e.g., habitat homogenisation, to complete loss of specialised species or habitat fragmentation.

The realisation of the scale of this issue has led to the inclusion of peatland restoration targets in the 2021-2027 Land Use Strategy³, with an ambitious 250,000-ha restoration target by 2030. At the present time, the majority of public funding into peatland restoration flows into the Peatland ACTION programme, which has delivered more than 35,000 ha of groundworks to restore peatlands to date among a consortium of directly funded organisations (NatureScot, FLS, Scottish Water, CNPA, LLNPA, RSPB and various local authorities).

The Climate Change Act 2019 commits Scotland to net-zero emissions of all greenhouse gases by 2045. Scotland reports on its territorial emissions on an annual basis, via the submission of the UK National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory (colloquially referred to as the UK Greenhouse Gas Inventory, UKGHGI) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change⁴. In the UKGHGI, the emissions from the peatland sector are included in the wider land use sector (LULUCF) compilation, and are structured by land use class. For each land use class on peat (e.g., cropland), sectoral emissions are currently calculated using a combination of 'Tier 3 (bespoke models, applying to only the forestry sector at present), 'Tier 2' (country-specific) and 'Tier 1' (IPCC default) methodologies, both of which multiply the area of land occupied by a given land use with the specific emission factor for a given source of emissions (e.g., carbon dioxide, methane, dissolved organic carbon etc)⁵. Further detail on UKGHGI reporting for peatlands can be found within the

¹ https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/assets/documents/reports/cat09/2206220830_ukghgi-90-20_Main_Issue1.pdf

² <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-greenhouse-gas-statistics-2020/>

³ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-third-land-use-strategy-2021-2026-getting-best-land/>

⁴ https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/assets/documents/reports/cat09/2206220830_ukghgi-90-20_Main_Issue1.pdf

⁵ https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/library/reports?report_id=980

latest report on methodology changes⁶. The current (2023) suite of emission factors in use, which the Peatland Code is now also aligned with, have been recently published by Defra⁷.

To achieve Scotland's ambitious peatland restoration area target alongside achieving the net zero ambition, it is necessary to simultaneously target the most cost-effective sites for restoration and to monitor both the baseline condition and emissions of residual near natural and degraded land and that of restoration sites. During the period 2017-2020, ClimateXChange Scotland ran a series of stakeholder workshops and commissioned a report⁸ on scoping a national Peatland Monitoring Framework. This work picks up from this initial scoping phase and presents potential avenues for such a monitoring framework, in order to produce data that reduce the present uncertainties in peatland condition assessments and greenhouse gas emissions reporting.

Direct monitoring of greenhouse gas emissions as the major indicator of condition from a peat accumulation and net emissions perspective would be the ideal solution for a network of peatland monitoring sites, however the cost of monitoring is prohibitive beyond use for selected sites. There is, however, scope to use relatively low-cost water table loggers to establish a reasonable estimate of the net carbon emissions of peatland sites via the recently established strong relationship between mean annual water table depth and net carbon dioxide and methane emissions⁹. In order to upscale, data from such water table monitoring locations, alongside other low-cost indicators of condition such as simple classification schemes^{10, 11}, soil moisture dynamics¹², or peat motion dynamics as assessed with cameras¹³ could be used to parameterise national scale modelling approaches that utilise Earth Observations (EO).

At present, the emissions estimates for peatlands in the UKGHGI are of variable quality in terms of the robustness of the evidence behind the area calculations as well as the emission factors (see ⁷). Improving the area estimates for the land use sectors on peat is the focus of another Work Programme within this project (WP2) and will be reported on separately, although the design of the present work is taking into account the potential for such monitoring locations to function as ground validation for an Earth Observations-based national effort. In this WP1 report, we specifically concentrate on the design of an optimal network of monitoring sites, using low-cost proxies for condition and greenhouse gas emissions, under a future Peatland Monitoring Framework, covering the range of land use categories as reported in the UKGHI, while considering Scotland's climatic gradients.

The aim is that the Peatland Monitoring Framework will fit within the wider Soil Monitoring Framework currently being explored as part of the RESAS Strategic Research Programme and incorporates existing monitoring schemes such as the NatureScot designated site monitoring

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https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1132550/ghg-national-statistics-methodology-changes1990-2021.pdf#page11

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<https://sciencesearch.defra.gov.uk/ProjectDetails?ProjectID=21088&FromSearch=Y&Publisher=1&SearchText=peatland%20code&SortString=ProjectCode&SortOrder=Asc&Paging=10>

⁸ CXC Briefing note: A working paper – scoping a national peatland monitoring framework. [Scoping a national peatland monitoring framework | ClimateXChange](#)

⁹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-021-03523-1>

¹⁰ <https://research-scotland.ac.uk/handle/20.500.12594/24643>

¹¹ <https://www.nature.scot/doc/naturescot-research-report-1269-using-peatland-surface-motion-bog-breathing-monitor-peatland-action#Manual+Peat+Condition+Classification+Scheme>

¹² <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/10/6/903>

¹³ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2021.630752/full>

programme¹⁴, the specific monitoring of restoration sites under the Peatland ACTION programme¹⁵ and the existing multi-site, £1.5 m, infrastructure investment of eddy covariance-based GHG emissions monitoring (SCO2FLUX; Coyle et al., 2022¹⁶). This co-construction effort will maximise alignment of longer-term research effort on peatland overall condition, including their potential to contribute to net GHG reductions, regulation of water quality and flood risk mitigation, biodiversity, and (non)monetary values.

In this first progress report, we assessed the spatiotemporal representativeness of existing monitoring locations against an ‘ideal’ statistical design which aimed to balance monitoring locations across the uncertainties on peat locations and extent, gradient of climatic conditions, land use categories and socio-economic extremes across Scotland. We also assessed the sensitivity of low-cost alternatives to greenhouse gas emissions monitoring and provide an initial recommendation of a potential network design and the most critical locations of sites for new monitoring efforts.

Methodology

1. Statistical design of the optimal solution based on existing peat extent and land use data sources

In order to find a spatially balanced solution for a relatively low-cost monitoring network, we discussed network size and opted to test an automated statistical modelling solution to distribute a hypothetical 100 monitoring locations in the first instance¹⁷. These 100 locations were statistically distributed across the main peatland condition categories as per the UK GHG Inventory classification¹⁸, with the exception of drainage within each of these classes or the extent of bare peat within erosion, as such spatial data are not yet available at national scale (WP2 within this project is working on a remotely sensed data product to fill this gap by late 2024).

To limit the possible number of permutations that could be caused by the granularity / uncertainties in the peat extent mapping, number of land use categories and classes of climatic and socio-economic indices, we looked for pragmatic, coarse scale, solutions. To enable us to compare the potential impact of different peat extent maps (each created by a different modelling approach and/or model input data), we created a data product that intersected each of the peat extent maps in Evans et al. (2017)¹⁸, Aitkenhead et al. (2021)¹⁹ and Gagkas et al. (2022)²⁰ with identical land cover data as per the Evans et al (2017) methodology used to create the 1990 baseline in the UKGHGI. The land cover data comprised a spatial join of the Land Cover of Scotland 1988, which also forms the basis of the current UK GHG Inventory baseline, and the class 6 -7 land areas of the Land Capability for Agriculture map, which are an analogue for the ‘moorland’ or ‘upland’ line in Scotland. We used an identical ArcGIS-embedded python script as the one used for the original mapping for the UK

¹⁴ <https://www.nature.scot/professional-advice/protected-areas-and-species/protected-areas/site-condition-monitoring>

¹⁵ <https://www.nature.scot/climate-change/nature-based-solutions/peatland-action-project/how-apply/peatland-action-open-data>

¹⁶ Coyle et al. (2022) The Scottish GHG Flux Network - Review of site operation and data status - October 2022. Available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7386016#.Y8fUHITP3IU>.

¹⁷ A modelling solution based on 300 locations was also assessed but is not discussed in this report.

¹⁸ https://naei.beis.gov.uk/reports/reports?report_id=980

¹⁹ <https://www.climateexchange.org.uk/media/4859/cxc-peatland-restoration-and-emissions-savings-on-agric-land-final-feb-2021.pdf>

²⁰ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362468510_Spatial_disaggregation_of_a_legacy_soil_map_to_support_digital_soil_and_land_evaluation_assessments_in_Scotland

GHG inventory baseline work (work performed in 2015-2016, Evans et al., 2017) to classify the land cover. Using the UKGHGI method, areas that would be identified as extensive grassland under the LCS88 based component are being reclassified to modified bog if they fell on Land Capability for Agriculture classes 6-7. In the UKGHGI method, this additional step was included to resolve a clear anomaly with areas of ground being included as extensive grassland on areas where the LCS88 classification would have high degrees of classification uncertainties and that looked to be more likely to be *Molinia*-dominated bog when assessed against newer high resolution aerial imagery. Remaining areas that would still likely be extensive grassland on other LCA classes were left in the extensive grassland categories, and included e.g., former lowland raised bog margins converted to grassland. The harmonised method produced three output maps of land use classes on peat (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Illustration of the variability in extent and spatial location of peatland in different conditions classes when using three different modelled peat extent maps. Left - UKGHGI baseline peat map (Evans et al., 2017); Middle - Aitkenhead et al. (2021) and Right - Gagkas et al. (2022) map.

Sampling designs for 100 loggers were further stratified by climatic and socio-economic gradients. As a broad categorisation of climatic gradients, we used the meteorological regions as defined by the UK Met Office²¹ and as shown in Figure 2. Based on the three different maps of peatland extent between 51% and 58% of Scottish peatlands are in the Northern region, between 29% and 31% in the Western region, and between 13% and 18% in the Eastern region. For the socio-economic gradient, we used the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD, 2020) as a first indication. This compound index includes measures of health, income, education, employment, housing, access (rural services and isolation) and crime²². While this index is perceived to be more accurate in urban areas than in the rural regions of Scotland, it nevertheless forms a good starting point for potential monitoring locations, where, for example, local recruitment for the establishment and maintenance of such monitoring network could be considered. When intersected with the meteorological regions on the

²¹ <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/climate/maps-and-data/regional-climates/index>

²² <https://datamap-scotland.co.uk/scotland-deprivation-zones-on-a-map/simd2020-overall-deprivation-map/>

three peat extent maps, the resulting gradients of the SIMD on peatland areas broadly map along the meteorological divides, with a few notable exceptions (notably in the far South-West, and, to a lesser extent, within the Eastern Cairngorm region, Figure 2)²³.

Figure 2. UK Met Office meteorological regions of Scotland (left), and the Scottish Index of multiple deprivation (SIMD) 2020 extracted for peat areas (right).

2. Analysis of the sensitivity of low-cost monitoring alternatives of site condition and greenhouse gas emissions

Monitoring site condition of peatlands is labour intensive and has the potential to cause additional impact on such fragile ecosystems by trampling. Remote sensing-based alternatives that use freely available data from the Sentinel-1 (radar-based) or Sentinel-2 or other optical-based (e.g., Landsat, MODIS) satellites, show promising results but have not yet been fully tested at national scale. Some major progress has been made in testing both backscatter SAR for peatland water table depth modelling and interferometric SAR for more general peatland condition modelling, e.g.,^{24,25}, however, neither backscatter nor interferometric SAR-based models have been tested at national scale, although some good results have been obtained with local to regional pilots. Testing backscatter-SAR based modelling of water table dynamics (a proxy for site condition and greenhouse gas emissions) is part of the WP2 component of this project and thus reported separately.

²³ <https://www.gov.scot/collections/scottish-index-of-multiple-deprivation-2020/>

²⁴ <https://www.nature.scot/satellites-track-bog-breathing-help-monitor-peatlands>

²⁵ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/01431161.2022.2131478>

Monitoring greenhouse gas and aqueous carbon emissions from peatlands via the gold standards of eddy covariance-based or automated chamber measurements come at a high equipment cost and additional requirements for data analysis, requiring specialist skills. As referred to in the Introduction, the mean water table depth appears to be a robust proxy for at least carbon dioxide and methane emissions, and, given that the majority of Scottish peatlands are not regularly receiving high nitrogen loads via fertilisers or deposition, the majority of the gaseous carbon budget would be adequately explained with such a proxy. Methods to assess the losses via dissolved or particulate carbon routes have been addressed in Robertson et al., 2022²⁶.

In order to assess the minimum number of water level loggers per network location that would be required to obtain a reasonably robust site average of the mean annual water table depth, we looked at data from an existing network of logger installed by NatureScot Peatland ACTION which has been running for 5 years. The annual mean was calculated from each of 27 loggers present at the Flanders Moss site (Figure 3). In order to maximise the number of years of data available, the years were assumed to start on 1st April and end on 31st March. This gave five years of data from all but one of the loggers and four years for the remaining one. A similar method was used to that used by Allot et al. (2009) in which a large number of random sub-samples of a specified size were taken and the results were converted to a cumulative probability distribution.

In order to establish the frequency of sampling that would be required to obtain a reasonably robust mean average water table depth from each logger, we used a dataset of 7 loggers at an eroded blanket bog location at Balmoral Estate, where measurements had been made with very high (10 min) temporal resolution for the purpose of training and validating a model of groundwater flow. These data were subsampled to estimate the minimum observation frequency required.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the peatland ACTION water table data loggers used for the estimation of minimum number of required loggers.

²⁶ Robertson et al (2022) Analysing Carbon Losses from Peatland. Report on methodology for sampling and analysing peatland samples. Available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7386670#.Y8fXDoTP3IU>.

Results

1. Statistical design of the optimal solution based on existing peat extent and land use data sources

The outcome of the optimal allocation of monitoring points for each condition class in the context of the three peat extent models, stratified for climatic and socio-economic regions, is shown in Figure 4. It should be noted that some of the differences in the distribution of the sampling points are random (introduced by the model optimisation of the sampling locations) rather than being due to intrinsic differences between the three maps. The second issue to note is that the spatial data in the UK Greenhouse Gas Inventory do not yet include a differentiation between drained or undrained modified bog (this split is calculated using a national average estimate of the relative proportions) and that eroded bog categories are a mixture of modified bog and bare peat areas for the purpose of this report. Potential co-location of any 'ideal' monitoring locations relative to the drained/undrained modified bog, or the modified bog or bare peat components of eroded bog, would require further assessment.

Figure 4. Distribution of the statistically “optimal” monitoring locations, stratified by climate region and proportional cover of the UKGHGI major peatland condition classes on three different modelled peat extents: Left - UKGHGI baseline peat map (Evans et al., 2017); Middle - Aitkenhead et al. (2021) and Right - Gagkas et al. (2022) map.

Appendix Table 1 shows the allocations to land class that would be obtained if allocation was strictly proportional, and a target adjusted allocation based on having a minimum of 1 site in each land class in each region with sites for the remaining classes divided in proportion to the area of the class.

If a spatially balanced sample is selected for each class separately this gives the exact allocations required and ensures spatial balance in each class, but the overall spatial balance is not as good since there is no control over samples from different land classes being located close to each other. We

therefore iteratively created options with overall spatial balance using selection probabilities based on the adjusted allocations until one was found that had at least 1 site in each class and each region and for which the achieved number of sites in each class was close to the adjusted allocation for that class. We defined 'close' as being within 2 of the target number in the Northern region, where there are more sites, and between 1 of the target number in the Western and Eastern regions. The allocations achieved are also shown in Table 1. This method gives better overall spatial balance than selecting a spatially balanced sample for each land class separately but the balance within a particular land class may not be as good. The additional criterion of having each of the three climatic regions represented for each land class is intended to ensure at least some degree of spatial balance within land classes. The samples were selected using the local pivotal method implemented in the R package *SamplingBigData*²⁷.

Locations of existing monitoring efforts relative to the three 'ideal' network location solutions

Any national Peatland Monitoring Programme would ideally integrate into existing monitoring efforts. The largest of these is currently the Site Condition Monitoring Programme, which monitors the condition of features of special interest hosted on designated sites on a rolling programme, with a methodology agreed at UK level via the Joint Nature Conservation Committee²⁸. For peatlands, the monitoring methodology is specific for lowland²⁹ versus upland³⁰ peatland habitats. We assessed the number of 'ideal' network monitoring locations from this exercise against the locations of sites designated for any peatland interest³¹. We found that, depending on which of the three model outcomes were analysed, between 35 and 48% of the 'ideal' near-natural low-cost monitoring points fell within the boundaries of a designated site (SAC, SSSI, Ramsar or NNR). Due to time constraints, we have not yet been able to follow up on whether the exact locations coincide with the peatland interests within those boundaries, nor were we able to verify what the reported condition of these features were. This will form part of the next reporting period. As expected, only a low proportion of additional points were located within designated site boundaries. Where this occurred, this included only monitoring network sites that were assumed to be in a modified (eroded) or domestic extraction condition category, and hence are probably either edge features on designated sites and/or indeed indicative of the 15-18% of designated upland and lowland peatland areas in unfavourable condition³².

A second existing national scale monitoring programme of note is the ongoing monitoring of water table depths at a number of Peatland ACTION restoration project sites, after the site works were completed³³. We calculated the distance between these Peatland ACTION loggers and the nearest matching 'ideal' network locations for each of the three modelling outcomes. The results for sites with an 'ideal' network location within 10 km of a Peatland ACTION logger can be found in Appendix 2. In short, there were a few locations for each of the 3 modelling outcomes that could potentially

²⁷ Jonathan Lisic and Anton Grafström (2018). *SamplingBigData: Sampling Methods for Big Data*. R package version 1.0.0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=SamplingBigData>

²⁸ <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/common-standards-monitoring-guidance/>

²⁹ <https://hub.jncc.gov.uk/assets/2ca75082-4246-4ec3-9472-08fbc24165a3>

³⁰ <https://hub.jncc.gov.uk/assets/78aaef0b-00ef-461d-ba71-cf81a8c28fe3>

³¹ <https://www.nature.scot/professional-advice/protected-areas-and-species/protected-areas>

³² <https://informatics.sepa.org.uk/ProtectedNatureSites/>

³³ <https://scotland.shinyapps.io/snh-peatland-action-hydrology-explorer/>

be matched with existing Peatland ACTION loggers on post-restoration sites, and which could provide data on useful pairs of pre- and post-restoration trajectories of site condition proxies.

Finally, we visualised the 'ideal' network solutions relative to the existing SCO2FLUX network of eddy-covariance based monitoring of greenhouse gas emissions. Most of the existing SCO2FLUX sites corresponded reasonably well with the relative distribution of 'ideal' network sites (Figure 5). For example, the eroded site Arnol SCO2FLUX station in the Isle of Lewis, and the Girlsta station on Shetland mainland, are both within 10 km of at least one 'ideal' eroded peatland monitoring network out of the three potential peat mapping efforts.

Figure 5. Locations of current SCO2FLUX network sites (triangles) shown relative to the 'ideal' logger distribution based on the UKGHGI baseline condition mapping (circles). The colour of the symbols relates to the condition category, with matching colours indicative of the same condition category. The Glensaugh station is not part of SCO2FLUX at this point but will form part of the wider network for dissolved and particulate organic carbon monitoring on eroded peatland (Please refer to WP4 reports in due course).

Sensitivity analysis of the likely density of loggers required per site and temporal resolution of observations

Over the four years for which all 27 loggers at Flanders Moss were available the mean water table depth was 115 mm below the surface of the bog, with a standard deviation of 65 mm. To have a 95% chance of being within 50 mm of this 'true' value, 7 loggers would be required. For very robust approximation of the 'true' value of the mean annual water table depth (as per the full 27 logger

dataset), 15 or more loggers would be where the mean converges (Figure 6). This result may have some limitations because Flanders Moss is a rewetted lowland raised bog where the hydrological unit may be a little easier to spatially define than in blanket bogs, and also because the spatial distribution of the existing loggers at Flanders Moss contain quite a few logger locations on the periphery of the site, where conditions will be expected to be more variable and drier than in the main body of the bog. The results are, however, similar to those obtained by Allott et al. (2009)³⁴ on an upland blanket bog site, although they found that the mean was more unstable when based on 10 dipwells or less and started to converge for 15 or more dipwells.

Analysis of the annual mean water table depth, if measurement intervals of 30 minutes, 60 minutes, or every 24 hours rather than 10 minutes were used, suggested that a single daily measurement would suffice for a relatively robust annual average across the 7 high-resolution datasets available from Balmoral Estate. Further analysis will look at whether reducing this to weekly to monthly measurements would similarly result in reasonably robust mean annual averages (i.e., whether manual dipwell measurements would be useful data).

Figure 6. Estimated annual water table depth shown as a probability, based on subsets of 5,10, 15 or 20 loggers out of a possible maximum of 27. Two climatically different years are shown, an average year on the left, and a drought year on the right, which nevertheless show similar outcomes. The other three years are shown in Appendix 3.

Costs and installation/maintenance needs for a 100-site network of water table loggers

Based on the above results, a 100-site network with only water level monitoring capacity, using an average of 7 logger per site, would cost approximately £105,000 in equipment cost at 2022 prices, if standalone loggers that would require an annual manual download were used. An additional estimated £20,000 in materials would be required for the installation of the wells that would house these data loggers. In terms of staff time, setup per site would require a single day, inclusive of travel, with 2 staff, and thus 200 person days. Depending on the site location, each site would

³⁴ https://pure.manchester.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/38525401/FULL_TEXT.pdf

require a single visit per year to download data and perform a manual water table calibration and dipwell displacement check. This could be performed by one person, i.e., 100 person days per year. Processing of the data via a central facility would take in the order of 50 person days for a network of 700 data loggers if automated data processing pipelines could be used. An initially more expensive design could use cellular telemetry devices, which would potentially reduce annual download and maintenance staff costs but is probably prohibitive of cost at present as these solutions are still in the order of >£1000-1500 per logger. Some annual maintenance costs would still be required even if such automated data retrieval options become more affordable. Basic annual or rolling site condition category checks that would generate a minimum of 7 'quadrat' (10 m if to be used as input for model training and validation with Sentinel series satellite observations) assessments for each of the 100 monitoring network locations would require an additional staff time of ca 3 hours for at least one person, excluding travel to and from site from the nearest road distance, in order to generate the associated contextual vegetation and condition information to validate the network location categorisation, and for further follow-ups to establish validation data for any remotely sensed condition via Earth observations. We estimate that two sites could generally be surveyed in a single working day, inclusive of local travel, if a network of local operators could be established and so the initial annual staff cost would be in the order of 350 person days. Subsequent visits for a low-cost network could be on a rolling 5-year programme, which would be in line with the verification timeline for Peatland Code projects as well as the initial site-based reporting currently required by the Peatland ACTION programme.

We did not yet explore the costs for other condition and greenhouse gas emissions proxies such as soil moisture loggers or peat motion cameras as these are still at a research-only stage and have not yet been fully explored in terms of their applicability to national scale monitoring.

Appendix Table 1. Proportional allocations, adjusted allocations giving a minimum of 1 sample in each class in each region, and those allocations actually achieved, for a possible design with overall spatial balance that meets the criteria. Region 1 denotes the Northern Met Office climate region, region 2 the Western region, and region 3 the Eastern region.

class	region	UKGHGI baseline			Aitkenhead et al. (2021)			Gagkas et al (2022)		
		proportional	target	actual	proportional	target	actual	proportional	target	actual
Cropland	1	0	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	1
Cropland	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	1
Cropland	3	0	1	2	0	1	1	0	1	2
Domestic Extraction	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1
Domestic Extraction	2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Domestic Extraction	3	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Eroded	1	9	9	9	10	9	8	7	7	7
Eroded	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2
Eroded	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	3
Extensive Grassland	1	0	1	2	0	1	1	0	1	1
Extensive Grassland	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Extensive Grassland	3	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	1
Forest	1	5	5	5	3	3	3	12	11	9
Forest	2	10	9	10	7	6	5	11	10	10
Forest	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	4	3	2
Industrial Extraction	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Industrial Extraction	2	0	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	1
Industrial Extraction	3	0	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	1
Intensive Grassland	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2
Intensive Grassland	2	2	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
Intensive Grassland	3	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Modified Bog	1	19	18	16	27	25	24	17	16	17
Modified Bog	2	10	9	9	15	12	13	12	11	12
Modified Bog	3	5	4	3	5	3	2	7	5	5
Near Natural Bog	1	18	17	18	17	16	16	12	12	12
Near Natural Bog	2	5	5	4	5	4	3	4	3	2
Near Natural Bog	3	3	2	1	4	2	1	3	3	2

Appendix 2: Nearest matching 'ideal' network locations and their condition class relative to the Peatland ACTION water table logger network. Only sites within 10 km of the PA network are shown.

Nearest PA Hydro logger ID	Distance between logger and nearest 'ideal' network site (km)	MetRegion	Ideal' matching network site condition category	Peatmap
PORTMOAK01	0.7	3	Cropland	UKGHGI
FLANDERSMOSSGW01	4.1	3	Forest	UKGHGI
SLAMBOGM01	4.8	2	Industrial Extraction	UKGHGI
BARLOSHM01	5.0	2	Forest	UKGHGI
ABERNETH02	5.7	3	Extensive Grassland	UKGHGI
CARRIFRAN1	6.2	3	Modified Bog	UKGHGI
BH6	7.0	3	Intensive Grassland	UKGHGI
GOATFELLO2	7.8	2	Near Natural	UKGHGI
DUNDREGG01	8.6	1	Modified Bog	UKGHGI
CORROURF02	9.1	2	Modified Bog	UKGHGI
NAIRNSIDE2	9.6	1	Modified Bog	UKGHGI
OCMOINEM21	10.0	2	Modified Bog	UKGHGI
BENLAWERS1	10.0	3	Modified Bog	UKGHGI
WESTERMOSS01	0.2	3	Near Natural	Gagkas
DUNDREGG01	2.6	1	Modified	Gagkas
LONGBRIDM6	4.4	2	Cropland	Gagkas
CORRIMONY2	5.5	1	Modified	Gagkas
000LENZIE	6.4	2	Forest	Gagkas
BH6	6.8	3	Industrial Extraction	Gagkas
0000EASTER	8.3	3	Modified	Gagkas
EDINGLASS3	9.1	3	Extensive Grassland	Gagkas
DALNACOP04	9.4	1	Modified	Gagkas
000LOWMOSS	9.8	2	Forest	Gagkas
BENLOMON02	2.1	3	Near Natural	Aitkenhead
RMOBALER01	3.1	3	Modified	Aitkenhead
CORROURF02	4.8	2	Eroded	Aitkenhead
ABERNETH02	5.0	3	Intensive Grassland	Aitkenhead
SLAMBOGM01	5.1	2	Industrial Extraction	Aitkenhead
BH6	7.2	3	Industrial Extraction	Aitkenhead
DUNDREGG01	7.2	1	Forest	Aitkenhead
000LOWMOSS	7.7	2	Forest	Aitkenhead
OCMOINEM21	7.8	2	Modified	Aitkenhead

Appendix 3. Additional years of outputs for the logger number requirements, inclusive of a box plot (lower right) representing the mean and 50% of values within the box, for 5-20 logger subsets.

